

Supporting information S1 for Hybrid LCA of French research activities reveals limited trade-offs for decarbonization strategies

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1 Supplementary methods

1.1 Extraction of EXIOBASE impact factors

We used the pymrio (Stadler, 2021) to extract impact factors (IFs) from EXIOBASE 3.8.1 input-output table for the year 2022 (IOT_2022_pxp). In the main text and in the following we use the notation used in the pymrio documentation (<https://pymrio.readthedocs.io/en/latest/terminology.html>).

If we note S the factor of production coefficients and L the Leontiev matrix we have

$$M = SL,$$

where M is the multipliers matrix, i.e. “total, direct and indirect, requirement factors for one unit of output”. M has units of impact/M€. Total requirements (i.e. environmental footprints) due to the final demand Y (in M€) in each of the 49 regions of the world considered in EXIOBASE is given by

$$D_{cba} = MY.$$

D_{cba} thus has units of impact. In the standard implementation of EXIOBASE 3.8, D_{cba} is a matrix with 126 rows, corresponding to the impacts considered in this version. As we use the impacts from Impact World+, in our case D_{cba} has 45 rows which are the midpoint and endpoint impacts of IW+. In all cases, D_{cba} has 9800 columns (i.e. 200 sectors x 49 countries). All the impacts associated to one year of final consumption in France are given, in python notation, by

$$D_{cba}^{FR} = D_{cba}['FR'],$$

‘FR’ indicating that only the columns corresponding to French consumption are considered. D_{cba}^{FR} thus has 200 columns, corresponding to the 200 sectors of goods purchased in France and produced all over the world with the production pattern of goods consumed in France for each sector. To calculate impact factors for goods purchased in France we compute

$$C^{FR} = D_{cba}^{FR}/Y^{FR}$$

where $Y^{FR}=Y['FR']$ is the total final demand in France in one year, C^{FR} having units of impact/€.

When we estimate the impacts associated to a relocalization of all goods production to France, we use instead

$$M^{FR} = M['FR'].$$

1.2 Calculation of purchases impacts

In our previous work we, provided a correspondence between the 1466 NACRES purchases categories used in French public research institutions and the sectors used in the USEEIO EEIO database (De Paepe et al., 2024). To make the correspondence between NACRES and EXIOBASE sectors we took advantage of the table of correspondences between single EXIOBASE sectors

and multiple USEEIO sectors in the file `matching_commodities_USEEIO_exio3.xlsx` downloaded from <https://ntnu.app.box.com/v/EXIOBASEconcordances/folder/167418511675>. We inverted this table to have a correspondence between a single USEEIO sector and multiple EXIOBASE ones and we injected it in the NACRES/USEEIO table to have a NACRES/EXIOBASE correspondence table, where a single NACRES category is assigned to several EXIOBASE categories. For each individual sector we used the value in C^{FR} and we averaged the values for each NACRES category, getting matrix N^{FR} with 1466 rows for purchases categories and 45 rows for IW+ impacts. Finally, impacts for each laboratory are calculated as an element-by-element multiplication of N^{FR} with A_{pur} the vector of purchases in € for each NACRES category for a given laboratory.

1.3 Specific choices for LCIA

The effect of contrails was taken into account for air travel by multiplying by 2 the CF for CO₂ emissions in ecoinvent. Inventories of water consumed directly by laboratories (in m³) were divided by 5 to take into account that 80% of the water returns to the environment.

In the IW+ version of EXIOBASE we set to zero the characterization factor of nuclear energy because it was clearly erroneous. More precisely, for the midpoint impact *Fossil and nuclear energy use (MJ deprived)* the entry *Domestic Extraction Used - Metal Ores - Uranium and thorium ores* (and also the *Unused* one), initially set to 5.6E+11 MJ, was set to 0.

2 Supplementary Figures and Tables

2.1 Tables supplementing *Methods* section

Table S1- 1. Detail of databases used.

Data type	Database name and version	url or doi	File name
Process-based LCI	ecoinvent 3.9.1	https://support.ecoinvent.org/ecoinvent-version-3.9.1	N.A.
	Agribalyse 3.1.1	https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.57745/B5DTRR	N.A.
Input-output-based LCI	EXIOBASE 3.8.1 (Mar 8, 2021)	3.8.110.5281/zenodo.4588235	IOT_2022_pxp.zip
Process-based LCIA	Impact World+ 2.0.1	10.5281/zenodo.8200703	impact_world_plus_2.0.1_expert_version_ecoinvent_v39.xlsx OR impact_world_plus_2.0.1_expert_version_simapro.csv
Input-output-based LCIA	Impact World+ 2.0.1	10.5281/zenodo.8200703	impact_world_plus_2.0.1_expert_version_exiobase.xlsx

Table S1- 2. Correspondence between activity categories in GES 1point5 and impacts in Impact World + and category and impact labels used in this work.

See file `activity_and_impacts_vs_clusters.xlsx` in Supporting information S6.

2.2 Figures and tables supplementing Figs. 2 and 3 in the Main Text

Figure S1- 1. Endpoint average per capita damages disclosed for all activity categories for our sample of research laboratories. Human health damage (left) and ecosystem quality damage (right) per activity category for the different impact categories. Foods and water are data from 2023, all the other data are from 2019. Complementary to Figs. 2B and 3B in the Main Text (same data).

Table S1- 3. Statistics of the distribution of DALY impacts across laboratories from Fig.2A in the Main Text. *rel_err* = *std/mean*, i.e. the relative standard deviation.

impact_cluster	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max	rel_err
climate change	2.36E-02	1.86E-02	4.08E-03	1.35E-02	2.07E-02	2.73E-02	1.50E-01	7.85E-01
human tox	7.65E-03	9.05E-03	1.15E-04	2.37E-03	5.29E-03	8.15E-03	4.63E-02	1.18E+00
other impacts	8.73E-05	8.08E-05	4.91E-06	3.07E-05	6.55E-05	1.17E-04	5.30E-04	9.26E-01
particulate matter	1.05E-02	1.17E-02	5.97E-04	3.96E-03	7.97E-03	1.15E-02	7.48E-02	1.11E+00
water availability	5.69E-03	2.28E-03	1.16E-03	4.58E-03	5.92E-03	7.10E-03	1.35E-02	4.01E-01

Figure S1- 2. Endpoint average per capita damages for electricity consumption in our sample of research laboratories for three different electricity grids. FR: the real electricity grid in France (same data as in to Figs. 2B and 3B in the Main Text), avg: world average electricity mix (Coal (38%), Gas(23%), Hydro (16%), Nuclear (10%), Wind (5%), Biomass (3%), Oil (3%), Solar (2%), data from IEA (IEA, 2025) and Table S1- 4, max: corresponds to highly carbonated electricity mix (here Australian one). To obtain the 'avg' and 'max' data we divided FR data by the damages associated to 1kWh production with 'electricity, high voltage, production mix | electricity, high voltage | APOS, S - FR' and then multiply them either by the damages associated to the 'World average electricity mix' process described in Table S1- 4 or by 'electricity, high voltage, production mix | electricity, high voltage | APOS, S - AU'. As in the rest of the paper, all impacts were calculated with IMPACT World+ Expert v2.0.1.

Table S1- 4. Ecoinvent model process for 'World average electricity mix'. These providers correspond to the input. Input and output flows are all D:Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply/35:Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply/ electricity, high voltage. Total input and output is 1 kWh.

Source	Provider	Share (%)
Coal	electricity production, hard coal electricity, high voltage APOS, S	38
Gas	electricity production, natural gas, combined cycle power plant electricity, high voltage APOS, S	23
Hydro	electricity production, hydro, reservoir, alpine region electricity, high voltage APOS, S	16
Nuclear	electricity production, nuclear, pressure water reactor electricity, high voltage APOS, S	10
Wind	electricity production, wind, 1-3MW turbine, onshore electricity, high voltage APOS, S	5
Biomass	heat and power co-generation, wood chips, 2000 kW electricity, high voltage APOS, S	3
Oil	electricity production, oil electricity, high voltage APOS, S	3
Solar	electricity production, solar tower power plant, 20 MW electricity, high voltage APOS, U	2

Table S1- 5. Statistics of the distribution of PDF impacts across laboratories from Fig. 3A in the Main Text. *rel_err* = *std/mean*, i.e. the relative standard deviation.

impact_cluster	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max	rel_err
Acidification (marine)	9.54E+02	7.14E+02	1.70E+02	5.46E+02	8.39E+02	1.14E+03	5.39E+03	7.48E-01
Acidification (terr+water)	5.55E+02	5.31E+02	8.01E+01	2.65E+02	4.39E+02	6.26E+02	4.29E+03	9.57E-01
climate change	5.17E+03	4.06E+03	8.92E+02	2.95E+03	4.52E+03	5.97E+03	3.28E+04	7.85E-01
land use	1.42E+03	1.48E+03	1.57E+02	7.37E+02	1.16E+03	1.64E+03	1.38E+04	1.04E+00
other impacts	6.74E+01	5.80E+01	9.54E+00	3.70E+01	5.65E+01	7.82E+01	5.08E+02	8.60E-01

Figure S1- 3. Human health damage per laboratory vs. climate change damage in DALY for 2019. *r* is the Pearson correlation coefficient.

2019

Figure S1-4. Ecosystem quality damage per laboratory vs. climate change damage in PDF for 2023. *r* is the Pearson correlation coefficient.

2.3 Tobacco and air pollution health damages in France

Values were extracted from <https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-compare/#>, from the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, University of Washington (Ferrari et al., 2024).

Data 2019 for France				
TOBACCO		Population	Damages by the research sector per capita per year	
8.50E-04	deaths /hab	6.80E+07	57800	deaths/FR
0.024	DALY/hab	6.80E+07	1.63E+06	DALY/France
28.2	DALY/deaths			
AIR POLLUTION				
2.90E-04	deaths /hab	6.80E+07	19720	deaths/FR
4.10E-03	DALY/hab	6.80E+07	2.79E+05	DALY/France
14.1	DALY/deaths			

2.4 Figures and tables supplementing Figs. 5 in the Main Text

For the re-calculation of air travel impact via EXIOBASE we converted the activity data for plane travel in each lab in km into number of trips with two categories: trip 'less_or_equal_to_3000_km' and trip 'greater_than_3000_km'. Then, the total cost of airplane travel for a lab within a year was calculated as:

$$\text{travels_per_type}['\text{travel.cost.euro}'] = \text{travels_per_type}['\text{less_or_equal_to_3000_km}'] * 100 + \text{travels_per_type}['\text{greater_than_3000_km}'] * 675$$

where 100 € and 675 € are the average tax-free price of a one-way Paris-Nice and Paris-New-York, respectively, by in Air France¹ in 2024 (Table S1- 6).

Table S1- 6. Ticket prices for a reference short- and long-haul plane trip in Air France in 2024. Geodesic distances were calculated with <https://www.greatcirclemap.com>.

	Ticket price, including tax (€)	Ticket price, excluding tax (€)	Geodesic distance (km)	Price/km (€/km)
Paris-Nice	130	100	695	0.14
Paris-New York	740	675	5869	0.12

Figure S1- 5. Ratio of endpoint damages of air travel calculated via Ecoinvent (standard method in the paper) or via Exiobase using an air-ticket price of 100 € for trip < 3000 km and 675 € for trip > 3000 km. Each distribution represents the data from our sample of 109 French laboratories in 2019.

¹ A breakdown of the price of an airline ticket (https://www.airfranceklm.com/sites/default/files/2024-03/afklm_fiche_tarifs_en_hr.pdf) Air France KLM, 2024

Table S1- 7. Median of air travel impact ratios between ecoinvent and exiobase impacts calculated from Fig S1-5.

Impact	Median of ecoinvent / exiobase ratio
climate change	0.78
human tox	0.10
land use	0.63
particulate matter	0.77
acidification (marine)	1.40
acidification (terr+water)	1.50

We used the ratios in Table S1- 7 to renormalize the results in Fig. 2A of the Main Text under two limiting hypothesis: OI-LCA (Exiobase) provides the right impacts and P-LCA (ecoinvent) needs to be corrected, or the opposite. To do so in Figure S1- 6B impacts from activities other than purchases were divided by factors in Table S1- 7, while in Figure S1- 6C shows purchases impacts multiplied by factors in Table S1- 7. The data suggest that human toxicity is the only impact that cannot reliably compared between the two subsystems hybridized in this work.

Figure S1- 6. Comparison of average human health damage per capita for (A) methodology described in the MT (same data as in Fig. 2A) and impacts corrected for (B) ecoinvent-related activities (all except purchases) and (C) EXIOBASE-related activities (purchases). Corrections are minor except for human toxicity impacts.

2.5 Multi-criteria and carbon footprint-only methods agree well on climate change midpoint impacts

The current work follows previous studies on the carbon footprint of research (Ben-Ari et al., 2024; De Paepe et al., 2024; Mariette et al., 2022), which used a similar hybrid approach combining process and EEIO-based LCA but relied on different databases for climate change emission factors (ecoinvent vs. ADEME Base Carbone for process-based and EXIOBASE vs. USEEIO for EEIO-based assessments). Figure S1- 7 compares midpoint climate change impacts for the same 103 laboratory inventories estimated with the two methods. At the scale of the average laboratory, the total carbon footprint estimated via the two methods differed by less than 1%. By activity categories, differences in average carbon footprints were larger, within the range of 10-50 %. The largest difference by source are devices (-50% emissions in the current implementation) which represent less than 2% of emissions. Then arrive commutes and electricity (+30%) due to differences between ecoinvent and Base carbone. All the other activity categories are within 20% change. When we compare the two methods for each laboratory the correspondence is also very good (Figure S1- 7).

Figure S1- 7. Midpoint climate change emissions for all the laboratories considered in the study, calculated either with the LCA method developed in this work or the carbon footprint method developed in earlier work (De Paepe et al., 2024; Mariette et al., 2022), noted Original1p5. Data are provided for the average laboratory (top left), for each activity and each laboratory (top right) and for the total of emissions for each laboratory (bottom).

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